

MEASUREMENT OF TENSILE PROPERTIES OF FIBRES USING A DCB-SPECIMEN

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ABSTRACT

Constitutive data are needed at extreme strains to increase the understanding of fracture processes. Ordinary tensile tests ends prematurely due to localization and large amounts of elastic energy stored in the specimens prior to fracture. A novel method is proposed to perform tensile tests using a double cantilever beam specimen. To verify the method a large specimen is developed and tested. Similar results are achieved with the present method as with more standardized methods giving confidence in the method. The specimen should be possible to minimise to provide data with small specimens.

1 INTRODUCTION

Evermore detailed models are used to study material fracture. As the length scale gets smaller in the models, the material data determined from standardized test procedures show their limitations, cf. e.g. [1]. As the length scale gets smaller, the material data determined from standardized test procedures show their inability to predict the behaviour at large strains. When performing a tensile test, the experiment is prematurely terminated due to localization and instability. Due to the physical size of a specimen, large amounts of elastic energy are stored in the specimen prior to localization. During softening associated with localized deformation, the energy can be released and the specimen fails dynamically. No, or very little data, can therefore be recorded after localization. A very rigid test machine improves the stability. However, the size of the specimens still leads to premature fracture. The situation is very different at a notch or at a crack tip. Here, extremely large strains can develop before a crack is formed and it starts to propagate. The relatively small material volume accumulating elastic energy leads to a more stable development of localization and the formation of a crack.

In the present paper, a novel technique is developed to perform tensile tests on very small specimens. At present, the technique is under development and a large specimen configuration is tested. This is to verify the theoretical foundation for the method before minimization. In this brief paper, we report the first studies using this technique. The paper is organized with a section on the theoretical background followed by a section on the simulations of the experiments, a section on the experiments, and a section with the results. The paper ends with a discussion.

2 THEORY

Methods to determine properties of adhesives using the Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) specimen are presented in [2]; later development is summarized in [3]. Provided the beams of the specimen can be modelled using beam theory and the adhesive is rigid-brittle, the specimen is unconditionally stable, [4]. This means that under loading by controlled displacement, the specimen provides stable crack propagation with a gradually decreasing force, F . Figure 1A illustrates the geometry.

Figure 1: A) Specimen with adhesive, B) Specimen with fibres.

Although the stress distribution is non-homogenous in the adhesive layer, it is possible to measure the stress-elongation relation for the adhesive. During monotonically increasing elongation w of the adhesive layer, the stress, σ , first increases linearly with the elongation w of the adhesive layer. This reflects the linear elastic properties of the adhesive. When inelastic properties limit the increase in stress, the elongation continues and it is possible to follow the development of σ as it decreases to zero. This corresponds to the state at the tip of a growing crack. The integral of $\sigma(w)$ forms a pseudopotential that theoretically can replace an elastic potential if no unloading from an inelastic state takes place during an experiment. If this condition is met, Rice's J -integral,

$$J = \int_S \left(W dy - \mathbf{T} \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial x} dS \right) \quad (1)$$

is path-independent, [5]. Here, W , \mathbf{T} , and \mathbf{u} are the strain energy density, and the vectors of traction, and displacement, respectively. The counter-clockwise integration path S has the outwardly directed unit normal \mathbf{n} . By taking an integration path at the start of the adhesive layer, J is given by,

$$J = \int \sigma dw \quad (2)$$

where w is the deformation at the first part of the layer and σ is the corresponding stress. With an alternative integration path following the outer boundary of the specimen, J is also given by,

$$J = \frac{2}{B} F \sin \theta \quad (3)$$

where θ is the rotation of the loading points and B the out-of-plane width of the specimen, cf. Fig. 1. By utilizing the path independence, the two expressions are set equal and after differentiation, the stress-elongation relation for the adhesive layer is given by,

$$\sigma = \frac{\partial J}{\partial w} \quad (4)$$

The stress derived here is the first Piola-Kirchhoff stress, [6]. In an experiment, the loading points are gradually separated and the reaction force F , the rotation at the loading point, θ , and the elongation of the layer, w , are measured continuously. Thereafter J is formed using Eq. (3) and differentiated according to Eq. (4) to form the $\sigma(w)$ -relation for the adhesive.

Earlier studies have been done with a reduced width of the fracture region cf. e.g. [7-9]. However, this method is now reformulated for the situation illustrated in Fig. 1B. Thus, the adhesive layer is replaced with a fibre wrapped around the two beams of the specimen. Provided the distance between each thread of the fibre in the x -direction is small enough, the fibres can be treated mechanically as a

continuum. With σ_f denoting the stress in the fibre, the homogenized stress $\sigma = \sigma_f \pi d^2 / (2BD)$, where D is the distance between the centre of each thread in the x -direction. With $D > d$ there is a space between the fibres; with $D < d$ the fibres are wrapped in more than one layer. We can now directly evaluate σ as derived from experimental data using Eq. (4) and change to the stress in the fibre using $\sigma_f = 2\sigma BD / (\pi d^2)$; the corresponding engineering strain equals w/l , where l is the length of the free fibre between the supporting points y_1 and y_2 , cf. Fig. 2B. By inserting the homogenised stress into Eq. (4) and using Eq. (3) the stress in the fibres is given by,

$$\sigma_f = \frac{4D}{\pi d^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial w} (F \sin \theta) \quad (5)$$

Figure 2: Two cross-sectional areas, A) circular B) rectangular with protruding corner.

3 SIMULATED EXPERIMENT

Numerical simulations are performed using the commercial software ABAQUS. The fibres are represented by non-linear spring elements (SPRING1) and the beams are represented by beam elements (B21) with a circular cross section. A schematic sketch of the model is shown in Fig. 3. Due to symmetry, only one half of the specimen is simulated and each spring represents two fibres. The method to simulate the specimen with beam elements and non-linear springs has been used in several earlier studies, cf. e.g. [10]. Data representing the evaluated data for the present specimen is used in the simulations. In these simulations, the fibres are represented by non-linear springs between the centres of the beams. For a circular cross section, this is the same as the distance between point y_1 and y_2 . Convergence studies show that further reduction of mesh size and time step do not appreciably change the accuracy.

Figure 3: Schematic sketch of numerical simulations with non-linear springs.

4 EXPERIMENTS

In this initial study, a wire with the diameter $d = 0.72$ mm of a ductile low strength steel is used. Two types of experiments are performed. A: using a conventional experimental setup for wire testing, cf. Fig. 4A; and B: using the novel method which utilizes the DCB-geometry, cf. Fig. 4B.

For the conventional setup the fibre is supported by two cylinders giving the free length $L = 0.130$ m, cf. Fig. 4A. During the experiment, the displacement of the cylinders and the applied force are measured by the tensile test machinery (Instron 8872). The strain of the fibre is measured with an extensometer directly attached to the fibre. The extensometer is not shown in Fig. 4A. The quasistatic tensile test is performed at 0.1 mm/s.

For the DCB specimen two beams with a circular cross section and the diameter 20 mm are used. To secure a well-defined free length l for the wire, the wire is attached to the beams by use of an epoxy adhesive (SikaPower-498). The wire is wrapped with a distance $D = 2$ mm. That is, between each thread of the wire is a spacing, $D - d = 1.3$ mm. The elongation, w , of the first thread is measured differentially with two LVDTs; one on the upper beam and one on the lower beam, cf. Fig. 4B. Since the beams are much stiffer than the wire, it is possible to measure the elongation as the deflection of the beams. The distance between the loading point and the first fibre is, $a_0 = 45$ mm. Two rulers are used to optically measure the rotations at the loading points. During the experiment, the rulers are observed with a time-synchronized camera (Nikon D300) that takes photos with an interval of 5 seconds. The rotations are evaluated after the experiment using image analysis and a Matlab code. Quasistatic loading at $10 \mu\text{m/s}$ is used. The displacement of the loading point and the applied force are measured by the tensile test machinery (Instron 8802).

Figure 4: Experimental result A: ordinary tensile test B: Test with DCB-geometry.

5 RESULTS

The evaluated nominal stress vs. engineering strain relations for both the conventional and the DCB-experiments are shown in Fig. 5. With both methods, a yield strength of about 220 MPa is measured. Moreover, plastic hardening appears larger and ductility smaller using the new method. However, the new method shows a decreasing stress with increasing strain above about 12 % strain. No softening is captured with the conventional method.

Figure 5: Experimental result A: conventional tensile test B: test with DCB-geometry.

Figure 6 shows F vs. load point deflection, Δ , for the DCB specimen and for the simulation which uses the material behaviour from the conventional test, i.e. curve A in Fig. 5. Non-linearity starts early in the experiment; after about 2 kN, the non-linearity is clearly visible. At about 7.6 kN the fibres start to break. After this point, the load decreases in an anticipated way. The simulation result shows good resemblance to the experimental result. The maximum force in the simulation reach 96% of the maximum force measured in the DCB-experiment.

Figure 6: Force vs. deflection of the loading point for the experiment with the DCB-geometry.

Figure 7 shows J vs. w for the DCB-experiment evaluated using Eq. (2) and $w = \epsilon l$. In the DCB-experiment for w larger than about 4.5 mm, J is virtually constant at about 1650 N/m. This indicates that the specimen is properly manufactured.

Figure 7: Measured energy release rate vs. elongation of the fibres.

Figure 8 shows the first fifteen threads at one side of the specimen when the applied force has started to decrease. Numbering the fibres from right to left, fibres 1, 2, 4, 5 and 7 are broken. Fibres 8 and 10 show necking.

Figure 8: First fifteen fibres at one side of the specimen. The load is applied at the right.

6 DISCUSSION

The comparison between the two methods to measure the stress-strain relation for the wire show some discrepancies, cf. Fig. 5. At present, these are not fully understood. Loading of the DCB-specimen results in tensile stresses in the wire at the loaded end. Further into the specimen, i.e. at larger x , cf. Fig. 1B, the two beams of the specimen are pressed together. This means that the experimentally evaluated pseudopotential W represents the monotonic stress-strain properties of the wire in the tensile part of the stress-strain curve. The compressive part of W represents the much stiffer contact properties of the two beams. This should not violate the requirement for J 's path-independence viz. that W is not allowed to be explicitly dependent on x . The measurement of the rotation at the end of the beam may be influenced shear deformation γ of the beams. The distance between the loading point and the first wire is rather small and with Timoshenko's beam theory, θ should be replaced by $\theta + \gamma/2$. A more plausible reason for the discrepancies is the positioning of the LVDTs to measure w . In the present experiments, the LVDTs are positioned at the first wire. However, the wire is represented by a homogenized continuum in the evaluation of the experiments. The elongation w should be measured at the start of this homogenized continuum. With the measurement point moved closer to the loading point, w would be measured somewhat larger. This would be reflected in the stress-strain curve by moving it to the right and to smaller stresses. Thus, a stress-strain curve in closer agreement with the results from the conventional method. Another possible source of errors is the fixation of the wire to the beams. The free length l of the wire can be more well defined, e.g. by a

design as sketched in Fig. 2B. However, there are no obvious signs of a breaking-up of the adhesive joining of the wire with the beams.

As anticipated, the experiments showed a stable deformation also after the wire starts to fracture. It should be stressed that the DCB-specimen is compliant which means that it does not put any hard requirements on the stiffness of the testing machine.

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